

2024

**ANNUAL REPORT
CF REGISTRY OF IRELAND**

Preface

We are delighted to publish the Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland (CFRI) 2024 Annual Report. This report summarises the data collected in the registry for the year 2024 across a number of core and clinical outcome data points. 2024 was a standout year for the registry, marked by continued growth and deepening engagement in both ongoing and newly launched research projects, international collaboration, and data quality enhancement initiatives, as well as providing leadership in the long-term sustainability of registries across Ireland.

During 2024, CFRI participated in the bi-annual ECFSPR meetings in Brussels and in Glasgow (January and June respectively). CFRI Head of Research, Prof. Laura Kirwan, continues to sit on the Executive Committee of the ECFSPR and represents the Irish registry on a number of working groups at these meetings. We were co-author on a number of abstracts presented at the ECFS conference and had 2 abstracts accepted from internal projects. Paul O'Regan, our Data Analyst presented a poster on the trends in modulator use and Dr Robyn Doherty, Head of Operations, presented a poster on exploring the feasibility of implementing patient reported outcome measures (PROMs) in the registry. Both posters were well received and have since led to further work.

Data quality remained a priority in 2024 as we continued the implementation of our data quality validation visit programme; annually these visits are undertaken at 2-4 centres and aim to assess the quality of the data in the registry by checking it at source (i.e., in the patient charts). In 2024, we conducted data validation visits in 3 centres (a mixture of adult and paediatric centres) and are pleased to report overall positive results, signifying the continued quality of the data within the registry.

Building on work from 2023, including an event and publication on the sustainability of registries in Ireland, 2024 saw the registry lead a multistakeholder taskforce called the Future of Registries Taskforce (FoRT). The 2023 publication has since informed a EURORDIS Open Academy course on rare disease registries. FoRT is made up of around 50 members representing a wide variety of stakeholders in the registry space, including, amongst other stakeholders, patients, researchers, clinicians, and industry. The aim of the group is to establish consensus on a better way of working to ensure the sustainability of all registries. The group met 4 times in 2024, which has since led to further work in early 2025.

CFRI were also delighted to be members of the organising committee of the Irish National Cystic Fibrosis Conference (INCF), held in early 2025. This important scientific conference has not been held since before COVID-19. The INCF is a conference primarily targeted at a clinical audience including all CF MDT members. As part of the organising committee, the latter half of 2024 was spent preparing for the conference, ensuring funding sources were secured, delegate registration administration, managing poster submissions and identifying both national and international speakers.

CFRI continued their collaborations in a variety of important research projects throughout 2024. These included RECOVER (Real world clinical outcomes with novel modifier therapy combinations in children with CF); ICOS part 2 (Irish Comparative Outcome Study of CF – Evaluation of the clinical, psychological and economic effects of the Cystic Fibrosis Newborn Screening Programme); working with the dental hospital in CUH in a study into oral hygiene in people with cystic fibrosis; and the global CF registries collaboration on the impact of

COVID-19 on lung function and nutritional status in people with CF. The registry also contributed summary data tables for the European Medicines Agency, data that is used for post-authorisation safety and efficacy studies. We continue to participate in the ECFS Telehealth for Cystic Fibrosis Working Group (THCF), led by Dr Tamara Vagg.

According to the 2024 patient survey, a total of 1,376 patients, who attended a CF clinic for care in 2024, are consented to provide data to the registry; this represents 94.6% of the total Irish CF population. CFRI cannot overstate the importance of this data in driving research to improve patient outcomes. CFRI continues to collaborate with the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). ECFSPR¹ reports that it now contains pseudonymised demographic and clinical data from over 56,000 consenting CF patients from 42 countries.

We wish to extend our thanks to a number of groups. Firstly, we wish to acknowledge the generosity of the patients, and parents/guardians, who give explicit consent to access their data; without this, there would be no registry. We would also like to thank the multi-disciplinary CF care teams across the country for their dedication and professionalism. Without their active participation it would be impossible to maintain a quality registry. We would like to extend our thanks to our board members for their guidance and support during the year. In particular, we would like to thank Mr Philip Watt. Philip resigned from the registry in 2024 and we would like to thank him for all his expert advice and input over his membership of the board. In his place, we welcomed Dr Sarah Tecklenborg. Last, but by no means least, we would like to acknowledge the CFRI team members who continue to work tirelessly to collect and prepare quality data that drives research - your dedication to CFRI is very much appreciated.

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Chairperson
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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Ed McKone'.

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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Godfrey J. Fletcher'.

Cover image: Blessington Lakes, Co Wicklow. Photo courtesy Prof Laura Kirwan

¹ <https://www.ecfs.eu/projects/ecfs-patient-registry/annual-reports>

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Registry Overview

CFRI is an independent charitable organisation. CFRI is a centralised registry collecting data across 11 CF centres in Ireland, see appendix for details. During 2024, CFRI had a team of 5 staff and multiple contracted staff based on-site at a number of centres.

In order to collect data on People with CF (PwCF), the CFRI operates on an informed consent basis, whereby individuals living with CF are not registered prior to informed consent being obtained. Adults living with CF and parents/guardians of children living with CF are invited to participate via their CF Multidisciplinary Team (MDT) team.

The introduction of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in 2018 gave us all more control over how our personal data is stored and used. As a result, we are required to ask all patients to re-confirm their consent for CFRI to collect their information. Our new consent forms are fully GDPR compliant and have passed a review process with the ethics committee of each CF Centre. CFRI are currently undertaking a programme of re-consenting all participants in our national registry.

The registry collects information about consenting participants' ²CF care from medical records and compiles this alongside information on other registry participants in a secure registry database before analysing the data. Analysed data can be used to develop a better understanding of the health of all people in Ireland with CF and the treatment they are receiving.

Summarised annual data is submitted to the ECFSPR; the ECFSPR accounts for over 54,000 patients across 40 countries in Europe. Following on from the upgrade to the third generation of registry software in 2022, the registry continues to consider how to evolve and retain CFRI's proactive role in contributing to improved outcomes for all PwCF.

Interested in getting involved?

Participation with the registry is voluntary and is encouraged. Registration with the CFRI is open to anyone currently living with CF in the Republic of Ireland. If you are an individual with CF, or a parent/guardian of a child(ren) with CF, and wish to participate with the registry, you can contact the CFRI (see below) or your CF care team.

Want to learn more about the registry?

² Note that while the clinics reported the patients as having attended, it may not always have been possible for CFRI staff to access the hospital charts and capture the data. There is also often a time lag due to processing of consent of new patients. Any discrepancies are investigated to optimise the completeness of the CFRI data collection.

2024 overview

2024 Data Highlights

Summary registry data, 2009-2024

The table below provides general summary information about people living with cystic fibrosis (CF) consented to participate in the Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland (CFRI).

Summary of the CF Registry of Ireland, 2009-2024					
	2009	2014	2019	2023	2024
Cumulative registered individuals¹	1,198	1,435	1,609	1711	1,726
Living registered individuals²	1,119	1,267	1,344	1,389	1,398
Deceased registered individuals	77	165	236	278	283
Lost to follow up	<5	<5	29	44	45
Individuals with encounter recorded during the year³	993 (87%)	1114 (87%)	1161 (86%)	1371 (98%)	1376 (98%)
CFRI coverage of individuals receiving care for CF in Ireland⁴	89.2%	87.8%	88.9%	92.3%	94.6%
Age at year end in years, median⁵	18.5	19.5	20.9	23.1	23.7
Age at diagnosis years, median⁵	0.38	0.34	0.26	0.22	0.21
Children (<18 years), N (%)⁶	546 (49%)	588 (46%)	566 (42%)	538 (39%)	528 (38%)
Adults (≥18 years), N (%)⁶	573 (51%)	679 (54%)	778 (58%)	851 (61%)	870 (62%)
Adults (≥40 years), N (%)⁶	43 (4%)	98 (8%)	163 (12%)	215 (16%)	243 (17%)
Females, N (%)⁶	475 (42%)	548 (43%)	568 (42%)	605 (44%)	608 (44%)
Total deaths reported, N (%)⁷	17 (1.5%)	20 (1.6%)	10 (0.7%)	10 (0.7%)	5 (0.4%)
Number of Transplants in reporting year	<5	22	8	0	4
Lung Transplants in reporting year ⁸	<5	20	7	0	0
Other Transplants in reporting year ⁹	<5	2	1	0	4
Number of Women with Pregnancies¹⁰				20	20

Notes:

¹ Living, deceased and lost to follow-up who are consented with the registry on the 28th of May 2025 with a diagnosis before 1st January 2025. Note that the number of registered individuals reported in a given year may change between annual reports due to diagnosis reversals.

² Registered, alive and not lost to follow-up on the last day of the reporting year.

³ Individuals with an encounter recorded during the year who were not lost to follow-up at the end of the reporting year.

⁴ Percentage registry coverage is calculated by performing a census of all CF centres of the number of PwCF attending they're centre and calculating the percentage of these who have provided informed consent with the registry to collect their data.

⁵ The median age is the value such that 50% of individuals are younger and 50% are older. This is the median of all individuals alive and not lost to follow up at year end.

⁶ Calculated as a percentage of individuals who were registered, alive and not lost to follow-up at year end.

⁷ Calculated as a percentage of individuals who were registered, alive and not lost to follow-up during the year of follow up.

⁸ Lung transplant includes double lung, unilateral lung, lobes, heart and lung.

⁹ Other Transplant includes kidney and liver.

¹⁰ The total number of women who were recorded as being pregnant during the year. Retrospective data is not available on this variable.

Since the inception of the CFRI in 2002, 1,726 individuals with CF have consented to join. In 2024, 30 individuals were newly registered, fifteen of whom were newly diagnosed with CF. At the end of 2024 1,398 individuals were alive and not lost to follow up; all variables in the demography, diagnosis and genotype sections of this report are based on this cohort. There was a total of 1,376 (98.1%) individuals with clinic visit (encounter) data recorded with the registry for 2024, and all clinical outcome data presented in this report are based on this cohort.

The median age of PwCF has increased by over four years since 2014, and now stands at 23.7 years, with 17.4% of people over the age of 40. During the 2024 year 20 women had a pregnancy recorded, 7 of which resulted in live births during the year. Eight pregnancies were ongoing at the year end.

Summary of the CF Registry of Ireland Encounter data, 2009-2024					
	2009	2014	2019	2023	2024
Lung Function¹	N=710	N=893	N=1,026	N=1,160	N=1093
Severe <40% ppFEV₁	14.1%	9.3%	9.5%	4.9%	5.1%
Moderate 40-69% ppFEV₁	27.8%	28.9%	24.4%	20.2%	20.0%
Mild 70-90% ppFEV₁	26.2%	29.2%	29.2%	24.2%	24.7%
Normal >90% ppFEV₁	31.9%	32.7%	36.9%	50.6%	50.1%
Microbiology²	N=993	N=1,114	N=1,161	N=1,371	N=1,376
Chronic Pseudomonas Aeruginosa	40.2%	31.2%	28.4%	6.5%	5.5%
Chronic Staphylococcus aureus	29.6%	32.0%	27.8%	13.3%	13.3%
Intravenous Antibiotics (IV)	N=993	N=1,114	N=1,026	N=1,371	N=1,376
% Children requiring IVs for Pulmonary Exacerbation (PEx)	33.7%	25.5%	27.1%	7.5%	6.8%
% Adults requiring IVs for PEx	55.4%	51.8%	45.4%	19.3%	16.2%
Hospitalisation	N=993	N=1,114	N=1,026	N=1,371	N=1,376
% Children hospitalised for PEx	27.4%	23.9%	24.8%	7.2%	8.7%
% Adults hospitalised for PEx	38.8%	41.8%	41.2%	15.8%	13.1%
Nutrition³	N=690	N=863	N=1,009	N=1,126	N=1,093
Underweight	5.1%	2.5%	2.6%	2.1%	1.9%
Normal weight	77.8%	74.8%	71.5%	63.5%	61.9%
Overweight	17.1%	22.7%	25.9%	34.4%	36.2%

¹PwCF aged 6 years or over that have not received a lung transplant, with FEV₁ measured during the year
²At least one positive sample recorded in the year
³PwCF aged 2 years and over with height and weight recorded during the year

Registry coverage of the CF population

Each year the Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland conducts a survey of all CF Centres in Ireland. The primary aim of this is to calculate the CFRI's rate of coverage of those receiving care for CF in Ireland within a year. The most recent survey conducted in January 2025 estimates that 1,454 individuals attended an Irish CF Centre in 2024 to receive CF care. Of the 1,454 listed individuals, 1,376 were registered with the CFRI, representing 94.6% of people receiving care for CF in Ireland in 2024.

The rate of coverage has increased from previous years. A decline was seen in 2020 and is largely due to the burden caused by the re-consent programme that we have been undertaking since the introduction of GDPR in 2018.

In 2024, there were 30 individuals newly consented to the registry, 15 of whom were newly diagnosed in 2024.

3

³ No patient survey was conducted for 2018.

Demography

Since 2002, the registry has collected information on PwCF in Ireland. This section provides demographic information of PwCF in 2024, including age, sex, and geographical distribution.

In 2024, there were more adults (aged 18 years or older) living with CF in Ireland than children. By the end of the year, 1,398 registered people were alive, of whom 528 were children and 870 were adults. The median age of PwCF in Ireland was 23.7 years, meaning half of the CF population was under the age of 23.7 and half was over the age of 23.7. The age of individuals alive in the registry ranged from birth to 75 years old, of whom 243 (17.4%) were 40 years or older.

Ten years ago in 2014, only 7.7% of individuals were aged 40 years or more, considerably less than the 2024 figure of 17.4%. The median age in 2014 was 19.5 years (IQR 10.0-29.7) more than 4 years younger than 2024 median age of 23.7 years (IQR 13.2-36.2).

As reported in other years, there were more males (56.5%) living with CF than females (43.5%). Similar differences have also been observed in other countries⁴.

In order to better understand the age distribution of PwCF, individuals were grouped into four-year age bands (0-3 years old, 4-7 years old, etc.), with those over 60 years grouped together. The age-bands with the greatest number of individuals were the 12-15-year-olds (n=137), followed by the 24-27-year old group (n=132). The number of males was equal to or

⁴ 2023 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). [https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report 2023 vs1.0 ECFSPR 20250507.pdf](https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report%202023%20vs1.0%20ECFSPR%20250507.pdf)

exceeded females across most age bands, with the exception of the 0-3, 8-11 and the over 60 categories.

The median age for females was 21.2 years (IQR 11.4-34.1) and 25.6 years for males (IQR 14.8-37.7). The difference in median age between the sexes was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Distribution of the number of people living with CF, registered with CFRI by county 2024

Created with Datawrapper

The counties with the largest numbers of individuals were Dublin (n=371), Cork (n=198), Limerick (n=76), Galway (n=73) and Tipperary (n=71). These figures reflect the county of home residence. The home address provided by individuals at registration was updated to reflect current county of residence where possible; where the person with CF's county of home residence was unknown the county of primary care centre was used.

Distribution of people registered with CFRI by province in 2024		
	Number	%
Connaught	144	10.3%
Leinster	708	50.6%
Munster	480	34.3%
Ulster	66	4.7%

When comparing the distribution of individuals living with CF who are registered with CFRI across the four provinces in the Republic of Ireland, over half (50.6%) were located in Leinster. Over one third of individuals lived in Munster, with the remaining 15% in either Connaught or Ulster.

Diagnosis

Early diagnosis of CF provides opportunities for earlier medical intervention. Providing infants with the best possible care may result in better nutritional and lung function outcomes later in life. In this section, we examine how and when individuals are diagnosed with CF, and how these trends compare to previous years.

Fifteen individuals registered with the CFRI were newly diagnosed with CF in 2024. However, this represents an underestimate of the total number of individuals diagnosed in 2024 due to the time lag between diagnosis and inviting newly diagnosed individuals to participate in the registry. Reports in subsequent years are adjusted as necessary to include those participants. For example, the number of individuals registered with the CFRI who were diagnosed with CF in 2023 is 19, with 9 of those reported as consented with CFRI in the 2023 annual report. The number of people receiving a new diagnosis of CF annually ranged from 15 to 39 across the decade.

Routine newborn screening for CF was first introduced in July 2011. The majority of individuals registered with the CFRI were diagnosed prior to the introduction of the screening programme. Early diagnosis of CF is vital for planning future management of the condition. In total 892 (63.9%) individuals were diagnosed with CF in their first six months of life, while 280 (19.9%) were diagnosed after their third birthday.

There are numerous circumstances and symptoms which can lead to a diagnosis of CF. Three hundred and eighty-five individuals had new-born screening (NBS) performed for CF. NBS leads to an early diagnosis, along with those with meconium ileus. Over 31% of individuals experienced respiratory symptoms leading to a diagnosis of CF. However, those individuals have a median age at diagnosis of over 1 year of age. In 2024, 19.7% of PwCF and registered with CFRI failed to thrive prior to their diagnosis, a family history of CF led to a CF diagnosis in 21.3% of cases and steatorrhea was indicated in 17.3% of cases. Before the introduction of NBS, the most common method for diagnosing CF was respiratory symptoms, with 41.5% of individuals presenting in this way. This compares with just 10.8% of individuals being diagnosed through respiratory symptoms after the introduction of NBS. There have been similar reductions in the number of individuals presenting with failure to thrive, steatorrhea and malnutrition after the introduction of NBS. This has led to a reduction in the median age at diagnosis from 5 months for those diagnosed before NBS to 1 month for those diagnosed since it's introduction.

Methods and median age of diagnosis of individuals living with CF in 2024									
Method of Diagnosis ²	All			Diagnosed Pre-NBS ¹			Diagnosed Post-NBS		
	% Individuals living in 2024 (n=1,398)	Median age at diagnosis (years)	IQR ³	% Individuals living in 2024 (n=943)	Median age at diagnosis (years)	IQR	% Individuals living in 2024 (n=455)	Median age at diagnosis (years)	IQR
All		0.21	(0.05-1.8)		0.41	(0.11-2)		0.06	(0.04-0.26)
Respiratory symptoms	31.5	1.19	(0.4-5.1)	41.5	1.02	(0.38-4)	10.8	7.85	(2.7-19.7)
Failure to thrive/malnutrition	19.7	0.47	(0.19-1.5)	26.8	0.48	(0.21-1.4)	4.8	0.24	(0.06-3.7)
Family history	21.3	0.12	(0.04-0.96)	23.9	0.14	(0.04-0.59)	16.0	0.07	(0.05-3.9)
Steatorrhea +/- abnormal stools +/- malnutrition	17.3	0.93	(0.24-3.2)	23.2	0.88	(0.25-3)	5.1	3.85	(0.07-5.1)
New-born screening (in Ireland/other country)	21.0	0.05	(0.04-0.07)	0.3	0.06	(0.05-0.08)	61.8	0.05	(0.04-0.07)
Meconium ileus:									
treated surgically	7.8	0.04	(0.02-0.07)	7.6	0.04	(0.02-0.09)	8.1	0.04	(0.03-0.06)
medically managed	4.4	0.04	(0.02-0.11)	5.8	0.04	(0.02-0.1)	1.5	0.06	(0.05-0.12)
management unknown	1.1	0.07	(0.04-0.22)	1.3	0.10	(0.05-0.28)	0.7	0.04	(0.03-0.06)
Other³	12.8	0.99	(0.08-6.6)	12.5	1.22	(0.18-5.4)	13.4	0.12	(0.05-11.3)

¹Diagnosis prior to introduction of the National Newborn Bloodspot Screening Programme for CF in Ireland in July 2011

²Multiple categories may apply to a single individual.

³Interquartile range (IQR) is a measure of the spread of data. It shows the mid-spread or middle fifty percent of the data, or the difference between the upper (Q3) and lower quartiles (Q1).

⁴Includes sinus disease, rectal prolapse, other neonatal intestinal/bowel obstruction, hepatobiliary disease, prenatal screening, prolonged jaundice, pancreatitis, electrolyte imbalance/dehydration, diabetes, infertility/genito-urinary abnormalities, clubbing.

Twenty-seven individuals identified as part of the National Newborn Bloodspot Screening Programme (NNBSP) in 2024 had a diagnosis of CF. By the end of 2024, twelve of those individuals were registered with the CFRI through consent from their parents or guardians. The statistics from the NNBSP are reported below.

National Newborn Bloodspot Screening Programme outcomes, 2024¹			
	2022, N	2023, N	2024, N
Total number of newborns² screened in NBS	54784	54820	54319
Number of samples with raised IRT sent to National Centre for Medical Genetics (NCMG)	799 (1.46%)	882 (1.61%)	828 (1.52%)
Number of newborns with one mutation identified	64	71	46
Number of newborns with two mutations identified	20	20	27
Number of newborns referred to a CF Specialist Centre	84	95	69
Number of newborns diagnosed with CF	21	30	27
Number of newborns diagnosed as carriers	60	62	40

¹Source: National Newborn Screening Laboratory, Children's Health Ireland at Temple Street

² Figures reported here are based on baby's date of birth.

The average incidence rate (the rate of new cases per 10,000 births in a given year) of CF in the population of newborns screened since 2014 is 4.5 people in every 10,000. In 2024 of the 54,319 new-borns screened, 27 were confirmed as having CF, an incidence of 4.97 people in 10,000 births (1 in 2,012 people).

CFTR gene mutations

CF is a genetic condition, whereby individuals inherit one copy (allele) of a defective Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane conductance Regulator (CFTR) gene from each of their parents. To date, approximately 2,000 CFTR gene mutations have been identified, each of which may cause varying levels and severities of CF disease. Vital information has been provided through genetic testing, which has assisted in diagnosing and treating CF and CF-related complications. This section examines the most frequently identified CFTR gene mutations in Ireland.

The F508del mutation was the most frequently identified CFTR gene mutation in PwCF in 2024, accounting for 73.2% of all alleles tested. Ninety-two percent of PwCF in Ireland have at least one copy of this particular mutation; this compares with approximately 80% in Europe³. Other common mutations in Ireland include the G551D mutation (15.4%) and the R117H mutation (6.0%). CFTR allele frequencies are shown below. In 2023 Ireland had the highest incidences of G551D mutation in Europe⁴.

CFTR allele frequency, 2024				
Legacy name	cDNA name	Protein name	% Allele frequency N=2,796	% PwCF with at least one copy N=1,398
F508del	c.1521_1523delCTT	p.Phe508del	73.2%	91.9%
G551D	c.1652G>A	p.Gly551Asp	8.3%	15.4%
R117H	c.350G>A	p.Arg117His	3.0%	6.0%
R560T	c.1679G>C	p.Arg560Thr	1.5%	2.8%
621+1G->T	c.489+1G>T	no protein name – splicing mutation	1.2%	2.4%
1717-1G->A	c.1585-1G>A	no protein name – splicing mutation	0.97%	1.9%
I507del	c.1519_1521delATC	p.Ile507del	0.72%	1.4%
G542X	c.1624G>T	p.Gly542X	0.64%	1.3%
V520F	c.1558G>T	p.Val520Phe	0.61%	1.2%
Other			9.1%	16.6%
Unknown ¹			0.68%	1.3%

¹Unknown may be due to genetic report not being available on patients file

⁴ 2023 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR).

https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report_2023_vs1.0_ECFSPR_20250507.pdf

In 2024, 54.5% of PwCF in Ireland were homozygous for the F508del mutation, meaning they carry two copies of the F508del CFTR allele. For European and neighbouring countries, the ECFSPR reported⁵ that for 2022, approximately 39% were F508del homozygous. A further 37.5% of the Irish CF population were heterozygous for the F508del mutation, meaning they carry one copy of the F508del mutation. This compares with approximately 42% in Europe. The remaining 8.0% of individuals carry no copies of the F508del mutation. The prevalence of the F508del mutation among PwCF across four-year age-bands is shown below.

⁵ 2022 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR).

https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/Annual%20Report_2022_ECFSPR_20240603.pdf

Encounter Data

People with Cystic Fibrosis should have regular outpatient/day care review by the specialist CF team every 3 months when medically stable and more often when they are unwell or unstable. The CF model of care⁶ outlines the principles of CF care which include, regular measurement of pulmonary function tests, nutritional support, treatment of exacerbations, respiratory physiotherapy, extrapulmonary manifestations of CF, as well as complications.

In 2024 1,376 PwCF consented with the registry had an encounter recorded with the registry. A breakdown of different health markers for adults and children will be outlined for these 1,376 PwCF, including microbiology, nutritional status, exacerbations of respiratory tract infections treated with intravenous antibiotics and hospitalisation. Regular medications and physiotherapy used by those with an encounter as well as complications are also captured below. Lung function tests for those aged 6 years and over only will be reviewed as well as the nutritional status for those who have had anthropometric measurements recorded in the given year.

⁶ <https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/cspd/ncps/cystic-fibrosis/resources/ncpcf-model-of-care-final-september-2019.pdf>

Lung function

Cystic fibrosis is a multi-organ disease. However, individuals' lungs are particularly impacted due to the failure of mucociliary clearance, mucus plugging and secondary infection. As a result, lung health is an important indicator of the overall condition of a PwCF. This is routinely measured using the Forced Expiratory Volume of air in the first second of an exhaled breath (FEV₁). Although this is measured in litres, it is often expressed as a percentage of the expected value from people without cystic fibrosis of the same age, sex, height, and ethnicity⁷.

Overall, 3,548 lung function measurements were recorded in 2024 from 1,093 individuals aged six years or older with no lung transplant in the CFRI. This compares with 3,405 (4% increase) lung function measurements recorded from 1,037 (5% increase) individuals for the same group reported in 2023. The lung function values recorded for individuals in Ireland for 2024 compares similarly to those reported in 2023 by ECFS for European and neighbouring countries⁴. For individuals aged 6-17 years, the median best lung function was 100.3% (IQR: 92.5-107.7%). This compares with a median of 98.8% (IQR: 87.7-108.3%) in the European data. For individuals aged 18 years and over, the median best lung function was 82.0% (IQR: 61.1-95.1%). This compares with a median of 79.6% (IQR: 58.6-95.8%) reported in the European data.

*Among individuals aged 6 years and older who have not had a lung transplant

⁷ Please refer to Appendix A for discussion around global lung function initiative equations.

⁴ 2023 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). [https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report 2023 vs1.0 ECFSPR 20250507.pdf](https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report%202023%20vs1.0%20ECFSPR%20250507.pdf)

Median best ppFEV ₁ by age and sex, 2024									
	All			Female			Male		
Age	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR
6-7	38	103.0	(94.9 , 111)	17	101.5	(95.9 , 110.1)	21	103.7	(94.6 , 114.7)
8-9	50	102.4	(94.1 , 111.5)	24	102.7	(93.7 , 112.3)	26	102.4	(95.2 , 108.3)
10-11	66	101.1	(94.2 , 107.9)	39	104.2	(96 , 110.3)	27	96.7	(91.6 , 105.1)
12-15	133	99.7	(92.1 , 106.2)	64	99.1	(88.5 , 106.2)	69	99.7	(92.6 , 105.6)
16-19	128	97.1	(88.9 , 105.8)	59	97.1	(88.4 , 102.8)	69	97.1	(89 , 107.4)
20-23	116	93.5	(81.1 , 101.4)	49	92.3	(78.6 , 100.6)	67	95	(82.8 , 101.6)
24-27	114	87.1	(70.8 , 99.8)	48	83.3	(70.1 , 96.3)	66	89.1	(71.1 , 100.1)
28-31	87	77.2	(56.5 , 93)	31	76.7	(60 , 93.7)	56	78.4	(55.5 , 91.9)
32-35	89	75.5	(56.2 , 91.1)	38	85.4	(58.6 , 94)	51	70	(55.7 , 87.1)
36-39	82	64.9	(51 , 85.9)	29	62.4	(52.5 , 71.8)	53	66.4	(51 , 87.6)
40-44	76	74.1	(55.5 , 87.1)	28	66.3	(49.3 , 82.3)	48	78.4	(56.8 , 87.3)
45-49	53	73.7	(51.5 , 93.9)	22	63.3	(46.1 , 95.2)	31	76.9	(61.6 , 91.2)
≥ 50	61	67.1	(46.3 , 83.8)	28	70.3	(53.5 , 88.4)	33	66.7	(45.4 , 81.1)
Total	1093	90.1	(69.7 , 101.3)	476	91.6	(69.3 , 102.1)	617	89.4	(70.7 , 101)

In 2024, females aged 6 years and over living with CF had a median best ppFEV₁ of 91.3% (IQR: 70.5-102.5%). This compared to 89.3% (IQR: 69.5-101.7%) in males. An independent samples median test of ppFEV₁ showed no significant difference between males and females (p=0.098).

CF is a chronic, progressive disease, which tends to become more severe as individuals get older. Both females' and males' median best ppFEV₁ decreases with age. Individuals living with CF between the ages of six to seven had a median best ppFEV₁ 103.0% while individuals over the age of 50 had a median best ppFEV₁ of 67.1%.

Lung disease severity can typically be categorised according to an individuals' ppFEV₁: ppFEV₁ <40% is severe; ppFEV₁ 40-69% is moderate; and ppFEV₁ ≥70% is mild or normal. In 2024, 96.4% of children had their best lung function measurements in the normal to mild lung disease range. This compares to 64.1% in adults (≥18 years). Over 7% of adults with CF had severe lung disease, compared to 0.3% of children.

Severity of lung disease, 2024				
	Severe ppFEV₁	Moderate ppFEV₁	Mild/normal ppFEV₁	
	<40%	40-69%	70-89%	≥90%
Children (6-17 years)	0.3%	3.3%	16.3%	80.2%
Adult (≥18 years)	7.5%	28.4%	28.9%	35.2%
All	5.1%	20.0%	24.7%	50.1%

Over the past decade, significant improvements in individuals' lung health have been observed in certain age categories. Increases in $ppFEV_1$ have been observed in PwCF between the ages of eight and thirty-five years and in the 40-44 years group. There was an average increase in mean best $ppFEV_1$ of 10.9% in 2024 compared to 2014.

Mean best $ppFEV_1$ over time													
	6-7	8-9	10-11	12-15	16-19	20-23	24-27	28-31	32-35	36-39	40-44	45-49	≥50
2009	95.0	92.9	90.5	78.1	72.4	63.3	63.6	59.2	55.3	57.8	63.1	60.3	50.8
2014	98.0	95.9	89.4	85.2	76.9	69.8	66.6	63.5	65.1	62.5	61.7	65.2	59.2
2019	97.2	99.2	93.7	88.9	83.3	77.4	68.4	66.1	61.6	68.5	62.5	60.4	65.5
2023	101.1	104.4	102.3	99.7	93.1	87.6	83.2	74.2	72.9	70.2	75.7	70.3	68.8
2024	101.2	101.2	100.1	99.1	95.3	89.1	84.0	75.2	74.2	67.3	70.2	71.3	67.9
p-values*	<0.001												

*If the p-value is below 0.05, then there is a statistically significant linear trend over time in $ppFEV_1$. Significant values are highlighted in bold.

Microbiology

One of the most notable characteristics of CF is recurrent exacerbations of lung infections. Due to thickened mucus in the lungs, bacteria may not be cleared easily. This may result in individuals with CF developing lung infections. Although a large range of organisms may contribute to these infections, there are a number of bacteria that are particularly prevalent.

The graph below shows the most common organisms detected in the airways of individuals living with CF in 2024. *Staphylococcus aureus* was found most frequently in sputum cultures from children, with prevalence of 50.4%. In 2024, 22.4% of children tested positive for *Haemophilus influenzae* at least once. This is similar to the 2023 figure of 25.4%. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was more frequently found in adults than in children. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was detected in at least one respiratory sample of 15.3% of adults compared to 4.4% of children. The prevalence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in adults in 2024 saw a reduction from 18.6% of adults in 2023 to 15.3% in 2024.

Other less frequently identified organisms found in the sputum cultures of PwCF in Ireland in 2024 included *Achromobacter* Species, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Burkholderia cepacia*. *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were detected in 16 people (1.2%).

Lung infections caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PA) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA) may become chronic. Chronic infections⁸ have a reduced likelihood of being removed from the lung, and often require long-term maintenance antibiotics. Furthermore, they may cause an irreversible decline in lung function.

In 2024, 66 (7.8%) adults and fewer than 10 children (<2%) had a chronic PA infection. This compares to 27.9% of adults and 8.1% of children in European data⁴. Chronic SA infection was reported in 52 (6.1%) adults and 131 (24.9%) children. This compares to 27.6% of adults and 27.8% of children in European data⁴.

⁸ Chronic infections are defined as having 3 or more positive reports of infection the last 12 month period preceding the last reported positive culture in the reporting year, or >50% of respiratory samples collected during the last 12 months (at least 4 samples) are positive, or if a patient was previously chronic and had at least one positive sample in the preceding 12 month period of the last reported culture in the reporting year.

⁴ 2023 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report_2023_vs1.0_ECFSPR_20250507.pdf

Since 2009 there has been a decrease in the percentage of PwCF reporting chronic PA and SA. Over 40% of individuals with an encounter in 2009 were reported as having chronic PA compared with just 5.5% in 2024. There has been a similar reduction in the number of PwCF having chronic SA from a height of 32% in 2014 to 13.3% by 2024.

Microbiology culture type by year					
	2009	2014	2019	2023	2024
Sputum Culture	3437 (58.2%)	2076 (57.5%)	1349 (59.5%)	956 (33%)	1146 (26.3%)
Cough swab	1118 (19.8%)	859 (20.9%)	818 (19.4%)	821 (26.8%)	931 (28.2%)
Throat swab	1018 (15.9%)	705 (16.7%)	750 (17.6%)	1052 (33.1%)	1148 (31.9%)
Other/Unknown*	199 (6.1%)	69 (5%)	144 (3.5%)	151 (7.1%)	246 (13.6%)
Total	6398	6342	5774	3471	3284

*Other type includes Bronchoalveolar Lavage, Nasal, Groin and Axilla swabs

There has been a downward trend in the number of culture samples with a 48.7% reduction in the number of samples attempted between 2009 and 2024. Throat swabs and cough swabs were the most common culture types in 2024 accounting for three fifths of all samples, at 31.8% and 28.2% respectively. The percentage of throat swabs as a percentage of culture type has almost doubled since 2019, possibly due to the effect of highly effective CFTR modulator therapies on sputum production.

Intravenous Antibiotics and Pulmonary Exacerbations

Intravenous antibiotics (IV) are a crucial component of CF care. IV antibiotics are used to treat chronic infections, reduce lung damage and improve respiratory function, especially during pulmonary exacerbations. A pulmonary exacerbation (PEx) is the development of a new symptom(s) or the worsening of existing symptoms, requiring treatment with intravenous (IV) antibiotics at home or in hospital.

During the year there were 314 IV antibiotic treatments required by 199 individuals, a reduction of 73.8% of total IVs compared with 2014. The most common indication for IV antibiotics was PEx which accounts for over 81% of all IV antibiotics prescribed. A total of 3,726 cumulative days were spent on IV antibiotics in 2024.

Number (%) of IV antibiotics				
Reason for IV antibiotics	2014 (N=1,200)		2024 (N=314)	
CF pulmonary exacerbation	1184	98.7%	255	81.2%
Other ¹	16	1.3%	32	10.2 %
Eradication therapy	0	0%	27	8.6%

¹Most common other IV indications included: Gastrointestinal illness, prophylaxis, haemoptysis, viral illness.

One hundred and seventy-four (12.6%) individuals had at least one PEx which required treatment with IV antibiotics in 2024. This compares with 13.2% reported in 2023. Of these, 36 were children (6.8%, compared with 7.3% in 2023) and 138 were adults (16.2 %, compared with 16.8% in 2023).

Of the 174 individuals who experienced at least one PEx in 2024, 53 (30.5%) had two or more. Although PEx are a common characteristic of CF, the majority of individuals do not require IV antibiotics. In fact, 93.2% of children and 83.8% of adults required no IV antibiotics. There has been an increase annually in the number of PwCF not requiring any IV antibiotics for PEx since 2009, with nearly 27% less children (<18) and over 39% less adults (18+) requiring IVs for PEx.

Overall, individuals living with CF spent 3,124 cumulative days on IV antibiotics (in hospital or at home) for a PEx in 2024. This compares with 4,424 in 2023. The mean cumulative duration of PEx treatment over the course of the year was 18.0 days (SD=±14.0) and median cumulative duration was 14 days (IQR: 9-24 days). Children generally had a similar amount of average time per IV antibiotic as adults (9.1 days vs 13.6 days). The overall average duration per PEx was 12.7 days (SD=±8.4), with a median duration per PEx treatment of 13 days (IQR: 8-14 days).

Duration of Pulmonary Exacerbation (PEx) treatment, 2024			
	Children N=36	Adults N=138	All N=174
Cumulative days on IV antibiotics	485	2,639	3,124
Mean cumulative duration of PEx treatment (SD)	13.5 (15.1)	19.1 (13.5)	18.0 (14.0)
Median cumulative duration of PEx treatment (IQR)	9.5 (4.75-14.75)	14 (11-27)	14 (9-24)
Mean duration per PEx treatment (SD)	9.1 (5.5)	13.6 (8.8)	12.7 (8.4)
Median duration per PEx treatment (IQR)	9 (4.75-13)	13.5 (9-14)	13 (8-14)

Hospitalisations

While some courses of IV antibiotic treatment for PEx may be administered at home, some individuals may need to be admitted to hospital for additional care. While PEx are the most common reason for individuals requiring hospitalisation, records in the registry reflect admissions for a variety of reasons, both CF and non-CF related.

In 2024, 270 individuals required hospitalisation. Overall, 401 hospitalisations were recorded for these individuals. This represents a 43% decrease from 2014. Over 54% percent of hospitalisations in 2024 were for the purpose of treating a PEx, compared with over 98% reported in 2014. There was an increase in the number of CF patients being hospitalised for other CF related reasons, from 1.4% of the hospitalisations in 2014 to 43.9% in 2024.

Number (%) of hospitalisations				
Reason for hospitalisation	2014		2024	
CF pulmonary exacerbation	698	98.6%	220	54.9%
Other - CF related ¹	10	1.4%	176	43.9%
Other - not CF related/Unknown	0	0%	5	1.2%
Total	708		401	

¹Most common other CF-related hospitalisations included: day case admissions for broncho-alveolar lavage, bronchoscopy, insertion/change/removal of gastrostomy tube, port-a-cath, haemoptysis and pneumothorax, amongst other reasons.

One-hundred and fifty-seven individuals (11.4%) were hospitalised for the treatment of a PEx over the course of 2024 (220 hospitalisations altogether). Of these, 46 were children (8.7% of children seen in the year) and 111 were adults (13.1% of adults seen in the year). Individuals in the 36-39 age group had the highest proportion of hospitalisations.

Of the 157 individuals hospitalised for the treatment of a PEx in 2024, 41 (26.1%) were admitted to hospital two or more times in the year. Despite this, the majority of PwCF required no hospitalisation for PEx, with 91.2% of children and 87.0% of adults not requiring admission for PEx.

Frequency of hospitalisation per patient

Age Group by year

0 1 2 ≥3

Overall, individuals living with CF spent 2,646 cumulative days in hospital for treatment of a PEx; this totals 709 days for paediatric care and 1,937 days for adult care. The mean cumulative duration of hospital stays for treatment of PEx over the course of the year was 16.9 days (SD=±13.8) and median cumulative duration was 14 days (IQR=9-21). Children generally spent less time in hospital for treatment than adults (9.1 days vs 14.0 days), and had a mean cumulative duration of 15.4 days compared to 17.5 days in adults. The average duration of hospital stays was 12.6 days (SD=±8.6), with a median duration per hospital stay of 12 days (IQR: 7-14).

Duration of hospital stay for pulmonary exacerbation treatment, 2024			
	Children N=46	Adults N=111	All N=157
Cumulative days hospitalisation	709	1,937	2,646
Mean cumulative duration of hospitalisation (SD)	15.4 (15.9)	17.5 (12.8)	16.9 (13.8)
Median cumulative duration of hospitalisation (IQR)	13.5 (6-17.8)	14 (9-21)	14 (9-21)
Mean duration per hospitalisation (SD)	9.1 (5.6)	14 (9.2)	12.6 (8.6)
Median duration per hospitalisation (IQR)	10(3.3-14)	13 (8.2-14.4)	12 (7-14)

Outpatient hospital visits

Individuals living with CF require regular outpatient visits to monitor the progression of their disease. The National Clinical Programme's Model of Care for Ireland recommends that medically stable individuals be reviewed by a specialist team every three months in an outpatient or day-care setting. The registry collects information on care delivered to individuals in a hospital outpatient setting.

In 2024, 7,448 outpatient visits by 1,377 PwCF to CF specialist centres and CF clinics across the country were recorded. Over 60% of these encounters were routine CF reviews or annual assessments.

In 2024, 17.3% of CF encounters happened virtually, either by phone or online. This is a continuation of the trend of increased virtual encounters post the implementation of health guidelines in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Number and type of outpatient hospital visits				
	2014		2024	
Routine CF Review /Annual Assessment	5505	84.8%	4612	61.9%
Virtual encounter	14	0.2%	1291	17.3%
Drop-in	204	3.1%	884	11.9%
Other*	765	11.8%	661	8.9%
Total	6488		7448	

*Most common other visits included: Blood tests, port-a-cath flush, home visits, starting medication, clinical trial visit, review of IV antibiotic levels, microbiology, pulmonary function testing, weight check, diabetic review, liver review, fracture clinic, dermatology clinic, A&E visit, transition visit.

Long-term medications

Certain medications are recommended for long-term use (typically for more than three months), to maintain health. These include long-term inhaled antibiotics for chronic lung infections and medications for CF-related complications, such as pancreatic insufficiency.

In 2024, Pancreatic Enzyme Replacement Therapy (PERT), a common treatment for pancreatic insufficiency, was the most frequently prescribed long-term medication, with 86.3% of individuals being prescribed PERT which is an increase of 3% since 2014. The other most commonly prescribed medications for regular use by individuals living with CF in 2024 were bronchodilators (67.6%) and mucolytics (67.6%). Over 53% of individuals used inhaled steroids which is the biggest increase in a single medication since 2014. Over 34% used inhaled antibiotics which has decreased by 10% since 2014.

Long-term medications, 2024								
	2014 Children <6 years N=183	2024 Children <6 years N=133	2014 Children 6-17 years N=385	2024 Children 6-17 years N=393	2014 Adult 18+ years N=546	2024 Adult 18+ years N=850	2014 All N=1,115	2024 All N=1,376
Pulmonary								
Mucolytic	59.6%	77.4%	85.5%	80.2%	60.8%	60.2%	69.1%	67.6%
Bronchodilator	40.4%	45.9%	51.7%	57.8%	53.1%	75.5%	50.5%	67.6%
Macrolides	7.1%	9.0%	40.3%	13.7%	64.1%	52.8%	46.5%	37.4%
Inhaled antibiotic	14.2%	3.8%	33.8%	6.9%	72.9%	52.6%	49.7%	34.8%
Inhaled steroid	9.8%	13.5%	17.1%	32.8%	14.3%	68.9%	14.5%	53.3%
Gastrointestinal								
Proton pump inhibitors	17.5%	15.0%	21.8%	18.3%	32.8%	60.4%	26.5%	44.0%
Pancreatic Insufficiency								
Pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy (PERT)	78.1%	81.2%	88.8%	82.4%	81.3%	88.9%	83.4%	86.3%

Burden of treatment is an area of concern for PwCF⁹. The treatment burden is higher in adults compared with children. In 2024 39.3% of adults (n=334) with an encounter in 2024 were prescribed three types of inhaled therapies, a reduction from the 44.8% reported in 2023. Only 2.7% (n=14) of children used all three types of inhaled therapies, which is a reduction from 5.0% reported in 2023. A further 282 (33.2%) adults used a mucolytic/bronchodilator (Muco/Broncho) and either an inhaled steroid or inhaled (Inh) antibiotic. This compares with 146 (27.8%) of children. Similarly for other medication 34.4% (n=292) of adults reported using all of PERT, Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPI) and macrolides while only 3.8% (n=20) of children use all three.

⁹ Rowbotham NJ et al, The top 10 research priorities in cystic fibrosis developed by a partnership between people with CF and healthcare providers. *Thorax*. 2018;73(4):388-390.

CFTR modulator therapies have transformed the management of cystic fibrosis by targeting the underlying cause of the disease, marking a major advancement beyond traditional symptom-focused treatments such as antibiotics, bronchodilators, and mucolytics. While these supportive therapies remain essential components of care, modulators represent a significant shift toward disease-modifying interventions. In 2024, four CFTR modulator therapies were licensed in Ireland, ivacaftor, lumacaftor/ivacaftor, tezacaftor/ivacaftor and ETI.

CFTR modulator therapy, 2024				
	<6 years N=133	6-17 years N=393	Adult N=850	All N=1376
CFTR modulator therapy				
Ivacaftor (% population)	19.5%	10.4%	9.5%	10.8%
Ivacaftor (% of those eligible)	100%	60.3%	42.4%	51.9%
Lumacaftor/ivacaftor (% population)	46.6%	7.1%	0.5%	6.8%
Lumacaftor/ivacaftor (% of those eligible)	92.5%	12.6%	0.9%	12.6%
Tezacaftor/ivacaftor (% population)		0.3%	0.9%	0.7%
Tezacaftor/ivacaftor (% of those eligible)		0.4%	1.7%	1.3%
Elexacaftor/tezacaftor/ivacaftor (% population)	55.6%	83.0%	74.9%	75.4%
Elexacaftor/tezacaftor/ivacaftor (% of those eligible)	80.4%	91.1%	80.9%	83.8%
Other		0.3%	0.2%	0.2%
Any CFTR modulator therapy (%population)	80.5%	93.1%	84.5%	86.6%
Any CFTR modulator therapy (% of those eligible)	93.9%	97.3%	86.6%	90.3%
Not eligible for CFTR modulator therapy	14.3%	4.3%	2.5%	4.1%

In 2024, ivacaftor was used as a monotherapy to treat PwCF aged one month and above with one of the following CFTR mutations: R117H, G551D, G1244E, G1349D, G178R, G551S, S1251N, S1255P, S549N and S549R. Overall, in 2024 ivacaftor was prescribed for 10.8% of Irish PwCF. This represents 51.9% of individuals who were eligible by age and genotype to receive the therapy.

In 2024, ivacaftor was used in combination with lumacaftor as a dual therapy for the treatment PwCF aged two years and older who are homozygous for the F508del mutation in the CFTR gene. In 2024, 6.8% of Irish individuals with CF received lumacaftor/ivacaftor, representing 12.6% of those eligible. The percentage of those eligible who were prescribed lumacaftor/ivacaftor was greater in children aged less than six years old (92.5%) than adults (0.9%). This was due adults having switched to an alternative CFTR modulator therapy in 2024.

In 2024, ivacaftor in combination with tezacaftor was used as dual therapy for the treatment of individuals aged six years and older who are homozygous for the F508del mutation, or who are heterozygous for the F508del mutation and have one residual mutation in the CFTR gene.

Overall, in 2024 tezacaftor/ivacaftor was prescribed for 0.7% of Irish individuals with CF. This represents 1.3% of individuals who were eligible by age and genotype to receive the therapy.

In 2024 ETI was used as a triple-therapy regimen for PwCF aged two years and older with one F508del mutation and one minimal function mutation or two F508del mutations in the CFTR gene. Overall in 2024, 75.4% percent of all Irish individuals with CF were prescribed ETI, representing 83.8% of those eligible.

In 2024 86.6% of individuals with CF in Ireland received a CFTR modulator therapy. At that time, 95.9% of individuals were eligible according to age and genotype to receive a modulator therapy, with 6.7% of children and 2.5% of adults being ineligible.

In 2024 some individuals met the eligibility criteria for more than one of the CFTR modulator therapy. Ninety-eight individuals switched modulator therapy during 2024. During the year 15 individuals stopped taking CFTR modulator therapy and did not restart, this means at the last encounter of the year 10.7% of those eligible to receive a CFTR modulator therapy were not receiving one.

CFTR modulator therapy use in those eligible at last encounter in 2024

■ Monotherapy ■ Dual Therapy ■ Triple Therapy ■ Eligible, No CFTR modulator Therapy

Airway clearance

Airway clearance is a vital element in the ongoing management of CF disease. There are a number of different airway clearance techniques which can be adopted by individuals. The primary aim of these techniques is to clear secretions from the lungs.

Airway Clearance Techniques (ACT) are often age-specific. The most frequently adopted ACT by adults is Autogenic Drainage (AD) and Positive Expiratory Pressure (PEP) for children.

Airway clearance techniques, 2024			
	Children N=526	Adults N=850	All N=1,376
Autogenic drainage	26.0%	55.4%	44.2%
Active cycle of breathing technique	3.6%	5.3%	4.7%
Positive expiratory pressure (PEP)	87.3%	52.2%	65.6%
Passive techniques	4.2%	0.6%	2.0%
Exercise	8.6%	0.2%	3.4%
Other	8.9%	8.0%	8.4%

Occasionally, in cases of severe CF disease, individuals may require oxygen therapy to maintain sufficient oxygen levels. Supplemental oxygen therapy may be prescribed to individuals for different scenarios, such as sleeping, exercising, or even for continuous use. Eight percent of adults living with CF in 2024 required oxygen therapy at home. Non-invasive positive pressure ventilation (NIPPV), such as BiPAP or CPAP, may also be used by PwCF. These treatments help clear mucus, improve breathing overnight and can improve exercise tolerance. Since 2014 there has been a reduction in the percentage of children requiring oxygen therapy and NIPPV. There has been an increase in the percentage of adults requiring NIPPV, while home oxygen therapy has remained stable.

Oxygen and non-invasive ventilation, 2024						
	2014 Child N=568	2024 Child N=526	2014 Adult N=546	2024 Adult N=850	2014 All N=1,114	2024 All N=1,376
Home oxygen therapy	2.46%	0.19%	8.06%	8.47%	5.21%	5.31%
Non-invasive positive pressure ventilation	2.46%	0.95%	4.76%	9.06%	3.59%	5.96%

Nutrition

Nutritional outcomes such as height, weight, and Body Mass Index (BMI) are an important measure of health in PwCF and can be expressed using a z-score. The z-score is a measurement that compares an individual’s height, weight or BMI with that of a comparable group of people living without cystic fibrosis. A z-score below zero implies that the outcome for the PwCF is below the predicted value of the non-CF reference group, and a z-score above zero implies that the outcome for the PwCF is above the predicted value of the non-CF group. Nutritional status has a strong correlation with pulmonary function and survival in PwCF¹⁰. Ensuring adequate growth and nutritional status in children with CF is a major goal for the MDT¹¹.

In order to examine the profile of nutritional health of individuals living with CF in 2024, the highest measurements of height, weight and BMI recorded in the year were considered.

¹⁰ Ashkenazi, M., Nathan, N., Sarouk, I. et al. Nutritional Status in Childhood as a Prognostic Factor in Patients with Cystic Fibrosis. *Lung* 2019; 197:371–376

¹¹ Castellani C et al, ECFS best practice guidelines: the 2018 revision. *J Cyst Fibros* 2018; 17:153-178

Children living with CF generally had median height Z-scores similar to that among children without CF. There were two exceptions for males in the 2-3 age groups and overall for all in the 12-15 age group, which were below the average but still within one standard deviation of the mean.

Median best height z-score in children and adolescents, 2024									
Age (years)	All			Female			Male		
	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR
0-1	31	0.58	(-0.1,1.4)	18	0.61	(-0.1,1.4)	13	0.55	(-0.1,1.1)
2-3	43	0.10	(-0.6,0.7)	25	0.37	(-0.1,1.2)	18	-0.21	(-0.7,0.1)
4-5	59	0.50	(0,1)	32	0.37	(0,1)	27	0.61	(0,0.9)
6-7	58	0.46	(0,0.9)	26	0.37	(-0.2,0.6)	32	0.57	(0.1,1.2)
8-9	53	0.29	(-0.4,0.9)	25	0.16	(-0.6,0.7)	28	0.35	(-0.3,0.9)
10-11	69	0.35	(-0.2,0.9)	40	0.02	(-0.6,0.5)	29	0.74	(0.3,1)
12-15	136	-0.14	(-0.8,0.6)	64	-0.14	(-0.8,0.6)	72	-0.14	(-0.9,0.7)
16-19	129	0.03	(-0.7,0.7)	60	0.13	(-0.7,0.7)	69	-0.02	(-0.5,0.6)
All	578	0.21	(-0.5,0.8)	290	0.18	(-0.6,0.7)	288	0.24	(-0.4,0.9)

Overall, children with CF in Ireland in 2024 had median weight z-scores which were above the mean of the non-CF reference group, although remaining within one standard deviation. This indicates adequate maintenance in nutritional status in PwCF under the age of 18.

Median best weight z-score in children and adolescents, 2024									
	All			Female			Male		
Age (years)	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR
0-1	31	0.25	(-0.5,0.9)	18	0.47	(-0.4,1)	13	-0.05	(-0.6,0.5)
2-3	43	0.49	(-0.2,1.3)	25	0.86	(0.2,1.4)	18	0.27	(-0.3,1.1)
4-5	59	0.63	(0.1,1.1)	32	0.55	(0.2,0.8)	27	0.85	(0.1,1.3)
6-7	58	0.50	(0.1,1)	26	0.37	(0.1,0.7)	32	0.73	(0.2,1.3)
8-9	53	0.14	(-0.3,0.8)	25	0.10	(-0.5,1)	28	0.22	(-0.3,0.8)
10-11	69	0.35	(-0.4,0.8)	40	0.04	(-0.7,0.6)	29	0.47	(-0.1,1.1)
12-15	136	0.18	(-0.3,0.8)	64	0.40	(-0.1,1)	72	0.04	(-0.7,0.6)
16-19	128	0.39	(-0.3,0.9)	59	0.51	(-0.3,0.9)	69	0.31	(-0.3,0.8)
All	577	0.36	(-0.2,0.9)	289	0.38	(-0.2,1)	288	0.33	(-0.3,0.9)

BMI is a metric that describes whether an individual is a healthy weight for their height. While limited, it is considered a good measure of nutritional status in CF. In order to examine the nutritional health of individuals living with CF in 2024, the highest measurements of BMI recorded in the year were considered.

In 2024, children living with CF in Ireland had median BMI z-score¹² higher than the mean of the non-CF reference group. Similar to median weight z-score, the median BMI z-score was mostly within one standard deviation of the mean.

Median best BMI z-score in children and adolescents, 2024									
	All			Female			Male		
Age (years)	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR
2-3	41	1.08	(0.3,1.4)	24	1.06	(0.5,1.4)	17	1.11	(0.1,1.5)
4-5	59	0.98	(0.3,1.5)	32	1.00	(0.5,1.3)	27	0.81	(0.3,1.7)
6-7	58	0.51	(0.1,1.3)	26	0.39	(-0.1,1.1)	32	0.59	(0.1,1.4)
8-9	53	0.29	(-0.2,0.7)	25	0.41	(0.1,1)	28	0.22	(-0.5,0.6)
10-11	69	0.3	(-0.4,1)	40	0.22	(-0.7,0.7)	29	0.49	(-0.1,1)
12-15	136	0.35	(-0.3,0.9)	64	0.72	(0.2,1)	72	0.10	(-0.6,0.7)
16-19	128	0.40	(-0.2,1)	59	0.51	(-0.1,1)	69	0.30	(-0.2,1)
All	544	0.42	(-0.1,1)	270	0.55	(0,1.1)	274	0.30	(-0.2,1)

¹² BMI z-score is only calculated for those aged 2 years and above.

The ECFS Standards of Care¹³ recommend a BMI of greater than 20 kg/(m²) in adults living with CF. In 2024, the median BMI of adults aged 20 years or older was 23.93 (IQR: 21.5-26.8). This is in line with the ECFS recommendation.

Median best Body Mass Index (BMI) in adults, 2024									
	All			Female			Male		
Age	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR	N	Median	IQR
20-23	111	23.12	(21.3,25.8)	48	23.55	(21,25.8)	63	23.02	(21.3,25.8)
24-27	115	23.60	(20.8,25.9)	48	23.12	(20.7,25.1)	67	24.11	(20.9,26.6)
28-31	94	23.68	(21.7,26.3)	33	22.56	(21.5,26.6)	61	24.03	(22.3,26.1)
32-35	100	23.74	(22.2,26.5)	41	22.95	(21,24.6)	59	24.37	(22.9,26.7)
36-39	97	24.09	(21.6,26.6)	34	22.96	(20.2,24.6)	63	24.74	(22.2,27.6)
40-44	91	24.19	(21.2,27.3)	30	21.98	(18.9,24.7)	61	25.01	(22.9,27.9)
45-49	64	24.47	(22.3,27)	27	23.46	(21.7,24.9)	37	25.35	(23.4,27.1)
50-54	40	26.10	(22,28.1)	16	26.66	(24,28.4)	24	26.08	(21.2,27.8)
55-59	19	26.29	(23.3,28.5)	6	26.39	(22.6,30.1)	13	26.29	(23.8,28.1)
≥60	14	26.14	(22.5,28.1)	9	22.99	(21,27.2)	5	26.84	(26.1,28.8)
All	745	23.93	(21.5,26.8)	292	23.09	(20.9,25.8)	453	24.43	(22.1,26.9)

In 2024, 52.3% of adults and 65.8% of children were in the normal weight category based on BMI and BMI z-scores. Over 44.9% of adult males were in the overweight category, compared with just over 27% of adult females. Only 2.8% of adults and 0.7% of children were in the underweight category. BMI category was not recorded for 5.9% of children and 6.9% of adults who had an encounter in 2024.

Nutrition Category % based on BMI (adults≥20) and BMI z-score (children<20), 2024						
	All		Female		Male	
	Children	Adults	Children	Adults	Children	Adults
Underweight (BMI <18.5 kg/m ² or BMIz <-2 SD)	0.7	2.6	1.0	5.8	0.3	0.6
Normal Weight (BMI 18.5-24.9 kg/m ² or BMIz -2 SD - +1 SD)	65.6	52.5	62.1	61.0	69.1	47.1
Over Weight (BMI ≥ 25 kg/m ² or BMIz ≥ 1 SD)	27.9	38.2	30.0	27.4	25.7	45.1
Not recorded	5.9	6.6	6.9	5.8	4.9	7.2

¹³ Smyth AR et. al, ECFS standards of care: best practice guidelines. J Cyst Fibros 2014; 13:S23-S42.

Since the introduction of CFTR modulator therapies in 2012 there has been a trend towards an increase in the percentage of children and adults reporting to be overweight in all age groups. For younger adults and adolescents there is a decrease in the percentage of individuals reporting as underweight.

In order to maintain or improve individuals' nutritional status, supplemental feeding may be required. Guidelines recommend differing interventions depending on the level of malnutrition¹¹, ranging from reinforcement of adherence to diet for anticipatory guidance, to feeding via Nasogastric (NG) or gastrostomy tube/button in severe cases of malnutrition. In 2024, over 40% of individuals with CF required supplemental feeding. Although most took oral supplements, approximately three in forty required gastrostomy tubes. Multiple approaches were adopted by some individuals in the reporting year.

Supplemental feeding %, 2024 (n=1,376)				
	Child <13 years	Adolescent 13-19 years	Adult ≥20 years	All
Any supplemental feeding	30.0	42.1	44.4	40.4
Oral supplements	27.4	37.4	36.5	34.4
Gastrostomy tube/button	1.7	6.8	10.2	7.5

¹¹ Castellani C et al, ECFS best practice guidelines: the 2018 revision. J Cyst Fibros 2018; 17:153-178

Complications

Individuals living with CF may develop a variety of complications. Complications of CF affect many organ systems, and can interfere with a person's health and quality of life. These complications often occur through the build-up of thick mucus in particular organs.

Gastro-oesophageal Reflux Disease (GORD) was the most frequently reported complication in CF in 2024, affecting 50.7% of adults. Sinus disease (40%), CF Related Diabetes (CFRD) either diet or insulin controlled (27.5%), and osteoporosis (17.9%) were also common among adults. As CF is a progressive disease, fewer children tend to suffer CF-related complications than adults. GORD (15%), sinus disease (5.5%), impaired oral glucose tolerance (OGT) (4.0%), CF-liver disease (4.8%) and nasal polyps (3.0%), were the most commonly recorded complications among children with CF in 2024.

Complications, 2024						
	2014 Child N=568	2024 Child N=526	2014 Adult N=546	2024 Adult N=850	2014 All N=1,114	2024 All N=1,376
Respiratory related						
Allergic Bronchopulmonary Aspergillosis	4.6	1.5	7.7	8.9	6.1	6.1
Nasal polyps	2.8	3.0	3.1	7.6	3.0	5.9
Asthma	1.9	1.5	7.3	13.9	4.6	9.2
Symptomatic sinus disease	4.0	5.5	35.5	40.0	19.5	26.8
Hepatobiliary & pancreas						
Elevated liver enzymes	5.5	1.0	2.4	0.2	3.9	0.5
Liver disease other than cirrhosis	1.6	3.0	5.9	14.2	3.7	10.0
Cirrhosis with portal hypertension	0.4	0.8	0.9	5.3	0.6	3.6
Cirrhosis without portal hypertension /portal hypertension unknown	8.8	1.0	11.2	2.6	10.0	2.0
Diabetes						
Insulin-treated CF Related Diabetes (CFRD)	4.0	1.3	27.8	22.7	15.7	14.5
Diet-controlled CFRD	0.2	0.6	5.1	4.8	2.6	3.2
Type 1 Diabetes	1.9	1.3	4.9	0.2	3.4	0.7
Impaired Oral Glucose Tolerance (OGT)	0	4.0	0	11.8	0	8.8
Gastrointestinal						
Gastro-oesophageal reflux (GORD)	33.1	15.0	61.5	50.7	47.0	37.1
Distal intestinal obstructive syndrome (DIOS)	3.5	2.9	6.6	6.5	5.0	5.1
Musculo-skeletal						
Osteopenia	1.4	0.4	14.1	17.2	7.6	10.8
Osteoporosis	1.1	0	32.4	17.9	16.4	11.0
Arthritis/arthropathy	0.5	0.4	2.2	3.2	1.3	2.1
Other						
Depression	0.4	0.6	8.4	8.2	4.3	5.3
Anxiety	0	2.1	1.3	10.5	0.6	7.3

While GORD is the most commonly reported CF complication across all age groups, there has been a decline of almost ten percentage points in the last decade. The number of PwCF presenting with osteoporosis has also declined by over five percentage points. There has been an increase in the number of individuals diagnosed with anxiety (6.7 percentage points), non-cirrhosis liver disease (6.3 percentage points) and symptomatic sinus disease (7.3 percentage points) in the past decade.

Age-related complications

With increased life expectancy in the CF population in Ireland, older adults with CF face increasing age-related complications like cancer and cardiovascular disease. While CFTR modulator therapies have improved clinical outcomes, ongoing research is crucial to address the long-term impacts on aging in CF.

In 2024 there were 26 PwCF with hypertension, 58% of whom required antihypertensive medication.

From 2006 to 2022 the CFRI recorded 13 cancers in PwCF. There were 12 PwCF reported as being diagnosed with cancer between 2023 and 2024. The median age at cancer diagnosis of PwCF treated for cancer between 2006 and 2022 was 27 years, compared with a median age at cancer diagnosis of 44 years for those treated in 2023 and 2024. The average of 6 cancer diagnoses per year from 2023-2024 corresponds with a rate of 1 per 233 individuals. This compares with an Irish population rate of 1 per 288.4 individuals (346.7 per 100,000) for all invasive cancers of the body excluding non-melanoma skin cancers in individuals aged 20-64 years¹⁴.

In line with the European patient registry CFRI has been recording the type of cancer diagnosed since 2023. In the last two years, colorectal, breast and testicular cancers have been the most commonly recorded types of cancer.

¹⁴ Published NCRI statistics, source: <https://www.ncri.ie/en/statistics/incidence-statistics> (accessed 24/09/2025)

Survival

As a result of developments in the management of CF disease, survival among individuals has improved dramatically in the last decade. However, PwCF still die younger than the national average, mostly as a result of respiratory failure¹⁵. The number of deaths varies from year to year. Since 2014, an average of 13 individuals have died annually (range: 5-20).

In 2024, 5 individuals with CF died (three female; two male), all of whom were registered with CFRI. The age at death was between 39 and 64 years old.

Of the 5 deaths in 2024, two (40%) were due to respiratory or cardiopulmonary causes and two were due to other CF-related reasons. The remaining death was cancer related. This is the lowest number of deaths recorded for a given year since the inception of the registry. Of the registered CF population, 0.72% died in 2024. This compares to 0.5%³ in the ECFSPR and 0.7%¹⁶ in the US in 2023.

The calculation of median predicted survival is based on PwCF who are recorded in the registry as alive in the given year. The median predicted survival predicts the age past which we can expect half of PwCF born today to live.

¹⁵ Stephenson AL et al, Clinical and demographic factors associated with post-lung transplantation survival in individuals with cystic fibrosis. J Heart Lung Transplant 2015; 34:1139-1145

³ 2023 Annual Report from the European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). [https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report 2023 vs1.0 ECFSPR 20250507.pdf](https://www.ecfs.eu/sites/default/files/general-content-files/Annual%20Report%202023%20vs1.0%20ECFSPR%20250507.pdf)

¹⁶ 2023 Cystic Fibrosis Foundation Patient Registry Highlights Handout <https://www.cff.org/medical-professionals/patient-registry>

Data from single years can show large variations in predicted median survival age from year to year which may be due to chance, and is not necessarily reflective of changing real-world outcomes. A rolling five-year predicted age of survival has been predicted and is presented below, as grouping together several years of data gives more robust estimates. The age to which half of individuals with CF born today are predicted to live to is at least 62.6 years. However, in recent years there is increased uncertainty in the predictions due to the decreasing number of observed deaths. The survival probability plot displays percentage of individuals surviving to a given age. The reference line at 50% indicates the estimated median. This estimate assumes that current age-specific mortality rates will not change for the rest of their lives. The approach does not take account of any potential benefits from future improvements in CF care, or the impact of CFTR modulator therapies on younger individuals.

	Total	Deaths	Median predicted survival age	95% CI
(2008 - 2012)	1241	94	38.5	(36.0 , 45.7)
(2012 - 2016)	1335	76	47.2	(42.5, 52.0)
(2016 - 2020)	1388	61	52	(50.1 , 61.1)
(2020 - 2024)	1429	47	62.6	(59.6 , not estimable)

Transplants

Lung transplantation is an established treatment for some people with severe or end-stage lung disease. Outcomes for people with lung transplantation continue to improve. In fact, five-year survival post-transplantation is greater than 80%¹⁷. The Irish National Lung Transplant Programme operates out of the Mater Misericordiae University Hospital.

The vast majority of lung transplant procedures for PwCF in Ireland take place at the Mater Misericordiae hospital. In 2024 no individuals underwent a bilateral lung transplant. This compares with 20 in 2014, the year in which the most bilateral lung transplants took place in the last decade. Since 2022, kidney and liver transplants have been more common than lung transplants.

Since the inception of the registry, 164 PwCF in CFRI have received at least one transplant. The median age of those living with a transplant in 2024 is over 38 years of age. The median age at transplant is 26 years, an increase of 2 years since 2009. Over 45% of people who received a transplant are aged over 40 years of age. Over 70% of those receiving a transplant are male, compared with 62% of the total CF population. The most common types of transplant that PwCF are living with in 2024 are double lung (81.3%), followed by liver (14.3%) and kidney (6.6%). However, there has been a dramatic decrease in the number of lung transplants reported compared to the numbers reported before the introduction of the highly effective CFTR modulator therapies.

¹⁷ Huang W, Smith AT, Korotun M, Iacono A, Wang J. Lung Transplantation in a New Era in the Field of Cystic Fibrosis. *Life* (Basel). 2023 Jul 21;13(7):1600.

Summary of PwCF who have received a transplant in CFRI, 2009-2024

	2009	2014	2019	2023	2024
Cumulative no. of registered individuals	50	109	155	160	164
Living registered individuals	47	91	109	89	91
Deceased registered individuals	<5	18	43	67	69
Lost to follow up	0	0	<5	<5	<5
Individuals with encounter recorded during the year, N (%)	46 (96%)	91 (96%)	112 (98%)	92 (97%)	91 (98%)
Age at year end in years, median¹	31.8	31.4	34.8	37.9	38.7
Age at Transplant in years, median¹	24.7	25.7	26.4	26.2	26.2
Adults (≥40 years)¹	28 (60%)	34 (37%)	34 (31%)	35 (39%)	41 (45%)
Females, N (%)¹	16 (34%)	31 (34%)	34 (31%)	26 (29%)	62 (30%)
Number of deaths	<5	<5	5	6	<5
Number of Transplants in reporting year					
Lung Transplants in reporting year²	<5	20	7	0	0
Other Transplants in reporting year³	<5	<5	<5	0	<5
Total Transplant Type^{1,4}					
Kidney	6	7	5	6	6
Double lung	36	77	97	75	74
Liver	6	8	10	11	13
Other Transplant Type⁵	5	6	<5	<5	<5

¹ Registered, alive and not lost to follow-up on the last day of the reporting year.

² Lung transplant includes double lung, unilateral lung, lobes, heart and lung.

³ Other Transplant includes kidney and liver.

⁴ Some individuals can receive more than one transplant so the totals may exceed the number with a transplant.

⁵ Other transplant type is lobes, heart & lung, unilateral lung.

Transplant: Clinical Outcomes

The total number of people reporting at chronic PA (3.3%) is slightly lower than the total adult population (7.8%). The number of people reporting positive SA (2.2%) is lower than the adult population (6.1%). The numbers requiring IVs and hospitalisation are comparable to the percentages reported for overall adults in 2024. Those who received a transplant have a higher proportion of individuals who were normal weight (70.5%) or underweight (5.7%) with a reduction in the percentage of individuals reporting as overweight compared to the adult population (23.9% vs 38.2%).

Summary of Clinical Outcomes for PwCF who have received a transplant, 2009-2024					
	2009	2014	2019	2023	2024
Lung Function	13	42	107	87	88
Severe <40% ppFEV₁	23.1%	30.8%	0.0%	46.2%	23.1%
Moderate 40-69% ppFEV₁	26.2%	28.6%	26.2%	19.0%	26.2%
Mild 70-90% ppFEV₁	7.5%	21.5%	37.4%	33.6%	7.5%
Normal >90% ppFEV₁	6.9%	31.0%	19.5%	42.5%	6.9%
Microbiology (N)	22	57	112	92	91
Chronic P. aeruginosa	18.2%	33.3%	17.9%	2.2%	3.3%
Chronic S. aureus	9.1%	10.5%	3.6%	2.2%	2.2%
Intravenous Antibiotics	22	57	112	92	91
% Requiring IV for PEx	31.8%	40.4%	25.0%	16.3%	17.6%
Hospitalisation	22	57	112	92	91
% Hospitalised for PEx	27.3%	36.8%	28.6%	13.0%	9.9%
Nutrition	20	49	104	88	88
Underweight	15.0%	4.1%	3.8%	6.8%	5.7%
Normal weight	75.0%	77.6%	73.1%	68.2%	70.5%
Overweight	10.0%	18.4%	23.1%	25.0%	23.9%

Transplant: Long-term medications

In 2024, all individuals who received a transplant required PERT this compares with 88.9% of adults in the total population. Similarly 96.7% of individuals required proton pump inhibitors, this compares with just 60% of the adult CF population. People with transplants also reported a higher usage of macrolides and inhaled antibiotics by almost 20%. A reduction in routine medication for 2024 for those with a transplant compared to the overall adult population is seen in the numbers requiring mucolytics, bronchodilators and inhaled steroids with a reduction of approximately 38%, 35% and 17% respectively.

Long-term medications, 2024		
	2014 N=57	2024 N=91
Pulmonary		
Mucolytic	47.4%	22.0%
Bronchodilator	24.6%	40.7%
Macrolides	75.4%	73.6%
Inhaled antibiotic	80.7%	71.4%
Inhaled steroid	5.3%	51.6%
Gastrointestinal		
Proton pump inhibitors	31.6%	96.7%
Pancreatic Insufficiency		
Pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy (PERT)	84.2%	100.0%

Transplant: Complications

Gastro-oesophageal Reflux Disease (GORD) was the most frequently reported complication in PwCF who have received a transplant, affecting 73.6% in 2024. This compares with 50.7% of the overall adult population. CFRD either diet or insulin controlled (61.5%), sinus disease (31.9%) and osteoporosis (47.3%) were also common among those who received transplants. The percentage reporting to have CFRD is much higher in the transplanted population compared to the overall adult CF population of 27.5%. Osteoporosis is higher in the transplanted population compared with the overall adult CF population (47.3% vs 17.9%). There is a reduction in the total number reporting sinus disease compared to the overall adult CF population (31.9% vs 40.0%).

Complications in PwCF who have received a transplant, 2024		
	2014 N=57	2024 N=91
Respiratory related		
Allergic Bronchopulmonary Aspergillosis	5.3%	8.8%
Nasal polyps	5.3%	7.7%
Asthma	3.5%	4.4%
Symptomatic sinus disease	15.8%	31.9%
Hepatobiliary & pancreas		
Elevated liver enzymes	8.8%	0.0%
Liver disease other than cirrhosis	14.0%	19.8%
Cirrhosis with portal hypertension	0.0%	11.0%
Cirrhosis without portal hypertension /hypertension status unknown	14.0%	1.1%
Diabetes		
CFRD Insulin	64.9%	57.1%
CFRD Diabetes	0.0%	4.4%
Type 1 Diabetes	3.5%	1.1%
Impaired OGT	0.0%	12.1%
Gastrointestinal		
Gastro-oesophageal reflux (GORD)	82.5%	73.6%
Distal intestinal obstructive syndrome (DIOS)	8.8%	2.2%
Musculo-skeletal		
Osteopenia	10.5%	29.7%
Osteoporosis	61.4%	47.3%
Arthritis/arthropathy	3.5%	2.2%
Other		
Depression	14.0%	6.6%
Anxiety	1.8%	7.7%

Applications for CFRI data

One of the CF registry's founding principles is to promote and facilitate the use of clinical data in approved research projects.

Requests for information held by the registry are assessed by the registry's scientific committee. If approved, data provided to third parties are anonymised (all identifiable data such as name, date of birth, home address, is removed). The data is summarised by the CFRI statistician and a report is prepared for the requester. This means that individuals in the registry cannot be identified from the data shared with third parties. In 2024, eight applications were approved. See <https://cfri.ie/data-applications-2/> for details.

The Irish CF registry contributes annually to the European CF Society Patient Registry (ECFSPR). The ECFSPR Annual Reports can be accessed here: <https://www.ecfs.eu/projects/ecfs-patient-registry/annual-reports>

Research papers & presentations in 2024

CFRI publications

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Financial information

Financial information for Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland CLG, 2024 Jan - Dec	
Income & Expenses	2024 €
Income	
Core Funding	140,000
Special Projects Grants	564,874
Unrestricted income	10,000
Other Interest receivable and similar income	3,148
Total income	718,821
Expenses	
Wages & salary	362,666
Employer's PRSI	29,935
Staff pension costs	14,195
External data collection	28,787
Rent payable	6,073
Insurance	932
Computer network & server costs	11,012
Software platform	58,336
Telephone, fax and video conferencing	1,600
Printing, postage and stationery	875
Travelling & subsistence	7,663
Legal & Professional Fees	1,414
Staff Training	2,175
Audit	4,059
Bank charges	372
Sundry expenses	1,918
Subscriptions	1,575
Depreciation of tangible assets	984
Total expenses	533,158
Operating (Deficit)/Surplus	181,716
Other interest receivable	3,148
Surplus before taxation	184,864

The full audited accounts were prepared by Hayden Brown, Chartered Accountants, Grafton Buildings, Grafton Street, Dublin 2 and copies are available upon written request to CFRI.

Acknowledgements

There are many individuals and groups that have contributed to and supported the work of the Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland during this reporting year.

We would like to thank all those who have financially supported the registry. This includes the HSE (through our Service Level Agreement), Cystic Fibrosis Ireland, our industry partners who have provided us with unconditional grants, and other funded researchers who have included us in their research grant applications. Without your support CFRI could not survive.

Most importantly we would like to thank each person with CF and/or their guardian for consenting for their medical data to be collected and used in a de-identified form to drive research into the development of new treatments and models of care for cystic fibrosis patients nationally and internationally.

We would also like to thank every member of the CF multi-disciplinary teams in every centre who assist our Research Associates in collecting data and assist in the patient consent process.

Our CFRI staff, Mr Paul O'Regan, Ms Soumya Joshy, Dr Robyn Doherty, Prof Laura Kirwan and our external data collectors who deserve special thanks for working tirelessly in the collection and preparation of quality data that contributes so much to CF research, service and treatment development, and quality management.

The CFRI board have been very supportive during the year and are always available when any assistance is required. We thank our research committee, GARC committee and finance & staff committee for their input during the year.

We would also like to thank UCD for supplying us with affordable accommodation through the sponsorship of the School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sport Science. We appreciate the support and mentorship of Prof Kelleher, Prof Fitzpatrick and their colleagues who have made an invaluable contribution to our own internal research programme.

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Appendix 1: Lung Function Reference Equations

Accurate interpretation of pulmonary function tests is critical in the diagnosis and management of cystic fibrosis.

Spirometry, which measures airflow and volume during inhalation and exhalation, is a standard tool in clinical practice for assessing lung function. Percent predicted FEV₁ (ppFEV₁) is closely monitored to assess an individual's lung function and disease progression, detect exacerbations, and measure improvement with therapy. It is often used to determine eligibility cut-off criteria for clinical decisions (e.g., transplantation, clinical trial participation). In 2012, the Global Lung Function Initiative (GLI)¹⁸ developed the prediction equations for spirometric indices, with the predicted values being calculated based on individuals' age, sex, height, and race. The equations were developed by analysing lung volume using data collected from individuals without established lung disease or a history of smoking. The 2012 equations used from data from many countries to establish race-specific reference values for groups categorised as white, African American, Northeast Asian, Southeast Asian, and Other. These race-specific 2012-GLI spirometry reference equations have been widely used in clinical care and research over the recent decade. In 2023, European Respiratory Society and the American Thoracic Society issued new recommendations to replace race-specific equations with the 2022 GLI race-neutral reference equations¹⁹. This was due to growing concern that use of race in lung function interpretation contributes to a false view of biologic differences in lung function between races and could mask the effects of social determinants of health. The 2022 GLI global race-neutral equations represent a weighted average of the original 2012 GLI data, resulting in a single set of reference equations.

For the Irish registry data we have presented the lung function results using the 2012 GLI reference equations to calculate ppFEV₁. In order to facilitate international comparison where the race-neutral equations have been used we present the lung function data below using both methods of calculation.

Over all age groups, there is a 5.3 percentage point increase in the median ppFEV₁ (90.0 compared with 95.3) when using the 2022 race-neutral equations for the Irish population. The difference between 2012 GLI values and 2022 race-neutral values differed significantly across age groups (p<0.001). There is less of a difference observed in those under the age of 12 with the race-neutral equations yielding a median ppFEV₁ only 2.3 percentage points

¹⁸ Quanjer PH, Stanojevic S, Cole TJ, et al. Multi-ethnic reference values for spirometry for the 3-95-yr age range: the global lung function 2012 equations. *Eur Respir J* 2012; 40: 1324–1343.

¹⁹ Bowerman C, Bhakta NR, Brazzale D, Cooper BR, Cooper J, Gochicoa-Rangel L, Haynes J, Kaminsky DA, Lan LTT, Masekela R, McCormack MC, Steenbruggen I, Stanojevic S. A Race-neutral Approach to the Interpretation of Lung Function Measurements. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2023

higher (101.8 compared with 104.1). The difference in median ppFEV₁ did not differ between males and females (p=0.139).

Median best ppFEV ₁ by age and sex, 2024												
Age	All				Female				Male			
	N	GLI 2012	GLI race neutral	Diff	N	GLI 2012	GLI race neutral	Diff	N	GLI 2012	GLI race neutral	Diff
6-7	38	103.0	104.3	1.2	17	101.5	103.7	2.2	21	103.7	106.2	2.5
8-9	50	102.4	104.1	1.7	24	102.7	103.4	0.7	26	102.4	105.4	3.1
10-11	66	101.1	104.2	3.1	39	104.1	107.0	2.9	27	96.7	99.4	2.7
12-15	133	99.6	104.9	5.2	64	99.1	105.1	6.0	69	99.6	104.3	4.7
16-19	128	97.0	104.2	7.2	59	97.0	104.7	7.7	69	97.1	104.0	6.9
20-23	116	93.5	100.5	7.0	49	92.3	98.6	6.3	67	95.0	101.7	6.7
24-27	114	87.1	92.9	5.9	48	83.3	88.5	5.2	66	89.1	95.0	5.9
28-31	87	77.2	82.7	5.5	31	76.7	82.7	6.0	56	78.4	83.3	4.8
32-35	89	75.5	80.9	5.3	38	85.4	90.6	5.2	51	70.0	75.3	5.3
36-39	82	65.2	69.2	3.9	29	62.4	66.6	4.2	53	66.8	72.0	5.2
40-44	76	73.3	78.4	5.1	28	66.3	69.6	3.3	48	77.2	82.6	5.3
45-49	53	73.7	78.0	4.2	22	63.3	66.8	3.5	31	76.9	82.5	5.6
≥ 50	61	67.1	71.8	4.7	28	70.2	74.5	4.3	33	66.7	71.5	4.8
All	1093	90.0	95.3	5.3	22	91.5	96.9	5.4	31	89.4	94.6	5.2

Appendix 2: Abbreviations

Abbreviation	
AA	Annual Assessment
ABPA	Allergic Bronchopulmonary Aspergillosis
AD	Autogenic drainage
ACT	Airway Clearance Technique
ADOLESCENT	Aged 13-17 years or older (13-17)
ADULT	Aged 18 years or older (≥ 18)
AMCNH	Adelaide and Meath Hospital Inc. the Children's National Hospital
BMI	Body Mass Index
BMT	Beaumont Hospital
CF	Cystic Fibrosis
CFLD	CF Liver Disease
CFRD	Cystic fibrosis-related diabetes
CFRI	Cystic Fibrosis Registry of Ireland
CFTR	Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane conductance Regulator (mutation)
CHILD	Aged under 18 years (<18) or under 13 years where Adolescent is used
CI	Confidence Interval
CRA	Clinical Research Associate
DIOS	Distal Intestinal Obstruction Syndrome
ECFS	European Cystic Fibrosis Society
ECFSPR	European Cystic Fibrosis Society Patient Registry
FEV ₁	Forced Expiratory Volume in one second
ppFEV ₁	FEV ₁ percent predicted
GLI	Global Lung function Initiative
GORD	Gastroesophageal reflux disease
HSE	Health Service Executive
IRT	Immunoreactive trypsinogen
IV	Intravenous
IQR	Interquartile range
MDT	Multidisciplinary Team
MRSA	Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus aureus
NBS	Newborn screening
NNBSP	National Newborn Bloodspot Screening Programme
NCMG	National Centre for Medical Genetics
OLCH	Our Lady's Children's Hospital, Crumlin
PAEDIATRIC	Aged under 18 years (<18)
PEP	Positive expiratory pressure
PERT	Pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy
PEx	Pulmonary exacerbation
PPI	Proton Pump Inhibitor
PwCF	People with Cystic Fibrosis
RCSI	Royal College of Surgeon's Ireland
SD	Standard Deviation

SVUH	St Vincent's University Hospital
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
UCD	University College Dublin
UHG	University Hospital Galway
UHL	University Hospital Limerick

Appendix 3: Technical notes

Data collection sites

In 2024, the CFRI gathered data from the eight HSE-designated CF specialist centres (Beaumont Hospital, St Vincent's University Hospital, CHI (Children's Health Ireland) group (including National Children's Hospital, Tallaght, Our Lady's Children's Hospital, Crumlin, Temple Street Children's University Hospital), University Hospital Galway, Cork University Hospital and University Hospital Limerick), three CF clinics (Cavan General Hospital, Sligo University Hospital, and University Hospital Waterford) and the Irish National Lung Transplant Programme at the Mater Misericordiae University Hospital Dublin. Following on from the CF census of Our Lady of Lourdes Hospital, Drogheda, which reported no CF clinics, data collection was not required in this centre in 2024. No data collection took place at Mayo University Hospital due to unavailability of data collectors to attend the centre.

Lung function

As spirometry cannot reliably be performed until the age of 6 years, only reported values for CF individuals aged 6 and older were considered. For individuals who were reported to have had a lung transplant in or before 2021, their FEV1% predicted values in the year of transplant and post-transplant were excluded. The best value of the year was considered. The Global Lung Function Initiative equations described by Quanjer PH *et al.*¹⁸ was used.

Nutrition

Heights and weights recorded at the patient's best FEV1% predicted of the year were included in the analysis. Where no spirometry was performed, the nutrition record with the best weight measurements in the year was considered. The reference group used to estimate Z scores was the Centre for Disease Control (CDC) 2000 reference charts.²⁰

Z-scores are a statistical measurement of the relationship between an individual's height/weight/BMI, and the mean of a group of reference individuals. A z-score of 0 means that the measurement (e.g. height/weight/BMI) is equal to the mean measurement of individuals of the same age and sex in the reference (i.e. healthy population). A z-score of -2 means that the value is two standard deviations below the mean of people of the same age and sex in the reference population, and a score of +2 means that the value is two standard deviations. The average score for a healthy population is typically zero.

¹⁸ Multi-ethnic reference values for spirometry for the 3-95 year age range: the global lung function 2012 equations'. Report of the Global Lung Function Initiative (GLI), ERS Task Force to establish improved Lung Function Reference Values, *Eur Respir J.* 2012; 40(6): 1324–43.

²⁰ Kuczmarski RJ, Ogden CL, Guo SS, et al. 2000 CDC Growth Charts for the United States.

Appendix 4: Members of the Board of Directors 2024

Prof Ed McKone	Chairperson	Consultant in Respiratory Medicine St. Vincent's University Hospital, Dublin
Prof Cedric Gunaratnam	Vice Chairperson	Consultant in Respiratory Medicine Beaumont Hospital, Dublin
Prof Basil Elnazir	Secretary	Consultant in Paediatric Respiratory Medicine Tallaght University Hospital, Dublin
Mr John Coleman	Treasurer	CF Ireland
Prof Gerry McElvaney		Professor of Medicine, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland & Consultant in Respiratory Medicine Beaumont Hospital, Dublin
Prof Paul McNally		Consultant in Paediatric Respiratory Medicine Our Lady's Children's Hospital, Crumlin
Prof Barry Linnane		Adjunct Associate Professor, University of Limerick School of Medicine, Paediatric Respiratory Consultant, University Hospital Limerick, Limerick
Prof Barry Plant		Director of Adult CF Centre, Clinical Director for Medicine, Consultant Respiratory Physician, Cork University Hospital, Cork
Mr Philip Watt	Resigned January 2024	Former Chief Executive CF Ireland, Dublin,
Dr. Sarah Tecklenborg	Appointed May 2024	Chief Executive Officer CF Ireland, Dublin,

Cystic fibrosis is an inherited condition that affects many body functions such as breathing, digestion, and reproduction. This lifelong condition usually becomes more severe with age and affects both males and females in equal proportions. The symptoms and severity of cystic fibrosis vary from person to person. The majority of people have both respiratory and digestive problems. There is no cure for cystic fibrosis. Life expectancy has increased steadily over the past 20 years, and today cystic fibrosis is no longer exclusive to childhood.

Better treatment strategies help to improve the length and quality of life of people with CF by controlling their symptoms. Improved treatments can be developed using patient registries. Cystic fibrosis registries gather information on all aspects of a patient's condition. They act as information storehouses for infection and treatment statistics. Detailed analysis of this information can yield significant findings about the most effective treatments for CF. It is through these analyses that better management of CF may be achieved.

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